

Reduced-Order Model with Geometry-Conforming, Voxel-Dominated Meshes for Neutron Transport

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a new reduced-order model (ROM) for fast and accurate solutions to neutron transport problems. It builds on previous work that develops and applies optimised space-angle basis functions to efficiently resolve the space-angle dimensions of the Boltzmann transport equation (BTE). An adaptation is introduced to enable the method's use with geometry-conforming structured grid meshes. The new method extends the ROM's capability to handle more general and complex domains, such as fuel-pin-level assemblies. The ROM maintains accuracy while reducing the discrete problem size and CPU solver times by several orders of magnitude compared to full-order models (FOMs) using standard discretisations. This is demonstrated on a quarter assembly of a 2D boiling water reactor (BWR) core, where accurate predictions of k_{inf} and neutron flux profiles are obtained under variations in moderator density. The approach reduces reactivity errors to within a few tens of pcm and achieves a substantial reduction in solver time.

Keywords: Reduced-Order Models, Neutron Transport, Geometry-Conforming Voxel Dominated Mesh

1. INTRODUCTION

The Boltzmann transport equation is fundamental to our understanding of neutron distributions in reactor cores, yet obtaining its solution remains a computationally intensive task. In part, this is due to the complexity of the core designs. Capturing geometric detail poses a significant challenge, often leading to exceptionally large computational meshes. Moreover, obtaining the BTE's solution is complicated by its inherent high dimensionality. Upon discretisation, the resulting linear system can become extremely large, potentially approaching the limits of computer memory and resulting in long solver times. Ultimately, without the accessibility of large HPC resources, large-scale problems require some form of simplification whether through homogenisation of the materials and geometry, or through the use of simplified equations such as diffusion theory.

Over the last couple of decades, reduced-order models have received a lot of attention for simulating reactor physics problems. Their attraction stems from their ability to provide high-fidelity solutions, with comparable accuracy to traditional high-resolution models, but using basis function sets with significantly reduced data storage requirements. This size reduction, typically exceeding three to four orders of magnitude in comparison to standard discretisation methods, leads to significant reductions in CPU solver times and memory requirements. Thus, they enable fast and accurate solutions, obtained with modest computing resources.

ROMs typically rely on the construction of optimised basis functions that resolve a particular class of problem within a limited domain (such as a reactor core). Solutions from full-order models (FOMs) - such as the finite element method (FEM) - are sampled over a small number of design space parameters,

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and the resulting solutions are approximated through methods such as singular value decomposition (SVD). The derived decomposition represents the fundamental modes that optimally capture the information of the solutions. These modes then form the basis functions that can be used to resolve other similar problem types.

For neutron transport simulations, a number of ROMs have been proposed, initially starting with diffusion-theory-based models: [1, 2] for eigenvalue calculations; [3] for the study of control rod movement; [4] for time-dependent problems; and [5] comparing ROMs to traditional nodal methods.

Later ROMs have been applied to the more involved transport equations: [6] for neutron transport within atmospheres, [7] for shielding applications, and [8, 9] for criticality problems.

Bespoke ROMs resolving the angular domain have also been investigated by a number of researchers, such as [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15], and more extensions have included angular adaptivity and domain decomposition [16] variants.

The method presented here uses a recently developed ROM that forms optimised basis functions resolving the space-angle phase-space dimensions of the BTE [17]. Initially developed using structured meshes with uniform resolution, the method is extended to enable its use with a new meshing approach, based on voxel-dominated structured meshes that are distorted to conform to arbitrary geometries.

To demonstrate the method, a section of a BWR fuel assembly is resolved and the ROM is assessed for accuracy in predicting reactivity under changing moderator density. Results demonstrate that the criticality k_{inf} errors are reduced to around 10pcm for problems not used in training, whilst accurately capturing the profiles of the flux solutions.

2. SPACE-ANGLE ROM FOR UNSTRUCTURED MESHES

This article focuses on the solution to eigenvalue form of the multi-group Boltzmann transport equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega \cdot \nabla \psi_g(\vec{r}, \Omega) + \Sigma_{t,g}(\vec{r})\psi_g(\vec{r}, \Omega) &= \sum_{g'=1}^G \int_{\Omega'} \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g}(\vec{r}, \Omega' \rightarrow \Omega) \psi_{g'}(\vec{r}, \Omega') d\Omega' \\ &= \frac{\chi_g}{4\pi k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'=1}^G \int_{\Omega'} \nu \Sigma_{f,g'}(\vec{r}) \psi_{g'}(\vec{r}, \Omega') d\Omega', \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

for obtaining the angular flux $\psi_g(\vec{r}, \Omega)$ (with \vec{r} and Ω denoting space and angle, respectively) for energy group $g \in \{1, 2, \dots, G\}$, and multiplication factor k_{eff} . Material cross-sections for total, scatter and fission are denoted by $\Sigma_{t,g}$, $\Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g}$ and $\Sigma_{f,g'}$, respectively, and the equation is accompanied by either void or specular reflective boundary conditions,

$$\psi_g(\vec{r}, \Omega) = 0, \quad \psi_g(\vec{r}, \Omega) = \psi_g(\vec{r}, \Omega^*), \quad \Omega \cdot n < 0, \quad \vec{r} \in \Gamma, \quad (2)$$

where Γ denotes the boundary of the domain, Ω^* is the incoming reflective angle to outgoing Ω and n is the outward-pointing normal to the surface.

In the following subsections, an outline of the space-angle ROM with geometry-conforming structured meshes is presented. The full details can be found within the listed articles, but it is the combination of these that forms the novelty of this article.

2.1. Optimised Space-Angle ROM basis functions and model

Traditional discretisations of the BTE for resolving the space and angle dimensions include the FEM and discrete ordinate (DO)/spherical harmonics methods. The angular treatment can be viewed as being

either an expansion of angular basis functions $\mathcal{G}_{g,j}(\Omega)$, for methods such as spherical harmonics, or as the solutions to the \mathcal{M} ordinate directions of the DO approach,

$$\psi_g(\vec{r}, \Omega) \approx \sum_{j=1}^{\mathcal{M}} \mathcal{G}_{g,j}(\Omega) \psi_{g,j}(\vec{r}) \quad \text{or} \quad \psi_{g,j}(\vec{r}), \text{ for } j \in \{1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{M}\}. \quad (3)$$

In either case, the angular treatment results in a set of spatially dependent coefficients $\psi_{g,j}(\vec{r})$, for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{M}\}$, that can be resolved using some spatial discretisation scheme such as the FEM. This can be written as,

$$\psi_{g,j}(\vec{r}) = \sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{N}} N_{g,j,i}(\vec{r}) \psi_{g,j,i}, \quad (4)$$

where $N_{g,j,i}(\vec{r})$ denotes the spatial FEM basis functions, and $\psi_{g,j,i}$ are the respective expansion coefficients. These can be substituted into the BTE to form a discrete set of equations for the eigenvalue problem.

$$A\psi = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} B\psi, \quad (5)$$

which can be solved using some solution process such as the Power method.

The discrete system of equations 5 are typically large due to the degrees of freedoms that the space, angle and energy discretisations introduce, which then multiply to form the total size of the system. To reduce the burden, it is possible to form optimised basis functions for use in equations 3 and 4 when there is knowledge of the problem type being resolved. More specifically, if one were to be scoping the parameter space of a problem, a small sample (say S) of "snapshots" of the discrete solutions to equation 5 can be generated from a full-order model - say using FEM+DO. The fundamental modes optimally capturing the information content can be generated through the use of singular value decomposition (SVD). These modes then form a new basis function sets for resolving problems of the same type as that of the of the snapshot data. That is, from the snapshot matrix S (of size $\mathcal{M}\mathcal{N}G \times S$), formed from discrete solutions ψ^i ,

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & & | \\ \psi^1 & \psi^2 & \dots & \psi^S \\ | & | & & | \end{bmatrix} \quad \Rightarrow \quad S = U\Sigma V^T \quad (6)$$

where the column vectors of U sequentially form the optimal basis vectors capturing the information of S . Hence these could be used to form the basis modes for resolving the BTE to similar problems. Here a novel approach is used that involves a 2-stage process that extracts the angular information of S to form optimal angular basis modes capturing the angular direction of particle transport. That is, rather than working directly with S in equation 6, a reduced snapshot data set is constructed by sampling the angular solution at a subset of spatial nodes. Specifically, s nodes are selected, and for each selected node j the corresponding angular vector $\psi_{g,j}$, containing all \mathcal{M} angular coefficients, is extracted. These vectors are then assembled to form a new snapshot data set $S^a \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{M} \times s}$. This also can be compressed via SVD, and reads as,

$$S^a = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & & | \\ \psi_{g,1} & \psi_{g,2} & \dots & \psi_{g,s} \\ | & | & & | \end{bmatrix} \quad \Rightarrow \quad S^a = U^a \Sigma^a (V^a)^T. \quad (7)$$

The sequential column vectors of U^a optimally capture the angular profile information, and hence the first $\hat{M} \ll M$ columns can be used to form optimal basis modes. Following this, one can then compress the snapshot data in equations 6 by projecting the full angular space of the FOM solutions onto the reduced angular space constructed from equation 7. From this, for each reduced angular coefficient j , a reduced snapshot data matrix is formed containing the spatial information S_j^s (of size $\mathcal{N} \times S$) and compressed via a SVD,

$$S_j^s = \left[\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} | & | & & | \\ \psi_{g,1}^j & \psi_{g,2}^j & \dots & \psi_{g,S}^j \\ | & | & & | \end{array} \right] \Rightarrow S_j^s = U^s \Sigma^s (V^s)^T. \quad (8)$$

The sequential columns of U^s optimally capture the spatial variation of the optimal angular basis function j . Hence, the first $\hat{N} \ll N$ columns of U^s can be extracted to form the optimal basis modes for angular coefficient j .

In summary, the two-stage approach first creates an optimal set of angular basis modes and then, for each angular basis mode, an optimal set of spatial basis modes is formed. These go directly into equations 3 and 4 and a reduced set of equations to 5 are formed of discrete size $\hat{M}\hat{N}G$ [17]. As mentioned, these are formed for an arbitrary approximations and have been used in DO and spherical harmonics, as well as continuous and discontinuous FEM formulations.

An added benefit of this two-stage approach is that it removes the need to operate on the full angular-space vector components simultaneously. Instead, much smaller snapshot matrices in equations 7 and 8 are generated and compressed, which helps mitigate memory issues when processing large angular vectors.

2.2. Geometry-Conforming Voxel-Dominated Meshes

In this article, the space-angle ROM method of Section 2.1 has been integrated with a new meshing approach using geometry-conforming voxel-dominated meshes recently developed in [18]. The meshing scheme aims to use uniform, structured voxel mesh elements as much as possible to discretise the problem domain. It is initiated with a background mesh, as presented in Figure 1 (left). When there is a need to preserve material interfaces, such as fuel pins and moderator, nodes of elements can be perturbed in order to preserve an arbitrarily orientated surface. The nodes identified to move are found via a signed distance field (SDF) approach that maps the distance of nodes to surfaces, identifies them, and moves them to the nearest points on the surface. The approach has the ability to move elements in a number of ways: to preserve the mesh internal and external domains to the surface, Figure 1 (middle), or to remove elements if only one region of the problem is required, Figure 1 (right). It allows the grid-like quadrilateral element structure to be preserved, Figure 1 (middle), or can cut elements into triangular/tetrahedral to fit the surface, Figure 1 (right). In this article, the grid-preserving mesh of the entire domain is employed for neutron transport solutions.

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE: AN 8 BY 8 PIN BWR ASSEMBLY

This section demonstrates the ROM's ability to accurately predict the reactivity of a BWR assembly. The problem domain, described in [19], is shown in Figure 2, consists of an 8×8 array of fuel pins and water columns. The pins have a radius of 0.599 cm and a pitch of 1.43 cm. Here, a two-dimensional k_{inf} criticality problem was solved, with reflective boundary conditions applied on all sides to represent an infinite array. A set of condensed two-energy-group material cross-sections was generated using OpenMC [20], defining two material regions: the pins (comprising fuel and cladding) and the surrounding moderator.

Using fuel and moderator temperatures of 900 K and 600 K, the moderator density was varied between

Figure 1. Left to Right: Voxel-based background mesh; Perturbed mesh conforming to a pin; Candu Assembly CAD model; Candu assembly mesh.

Figure 2. Left: BWR assembly with mesh - red indicates fuel, white water channels, and blue the coolant/moderator, Right: Close view of mesh showing 3 by 3 pins.

the range of $0.8\text{-}0.2 \text{ g/cm}^3$, at intervals of 0.1 , to replicate general conditions through the vertical sections of the assembly. The subset of densities $\{0.8, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2\}$ was used for generating snapshot data, for which the full-order model was solved to generate the ROM training data. The remaining moderator densities were used for testing the ROM's accuracy on examples different from those used in the training.

For the full-order model [18], used to generate the reference solutions and training data, a bi-linear discontinuous FEM discretisation was employed on a mesh of 9216 (96 by 96) quadrilateral elements, as presented in Figure 2, in combination with an S_{12} DO method. Figure 3 presents the thermal scalar flux solutions for two unseen problems with moderator densities of 0.7 g/cm^3 and 0.3 g/cm^3 . The exact solutions are compared with two ROM predictions of different resolutions: a high-resolution case, $ROM_{12,3}$, and a low-resolution case, $ROM_{6,2}$ (the subscripts denote the number of angular basis functions per octant and spatial modes, respectively), which result in discrete computational models of size 288 and 96. In both cases, the ROM is shown to capture the profiles of the flux solutions, as they compare closely to the exact flux. The ROMs have also captured the subtle changes in flux details arising from the changing conditions in moderator density, particularly around the regions of the water channels. The graph in Figure 4 presents the k_{inf} values as a function of the moderator density, in addition to the pcm errors of the ROM for different varying space-angle resolutions. It is shown that $ROM_{12,3}$ can reduce errors in k_{inf} to within 10 pcm, and that smaller $ROM_{6,3}$ models can keep errors within the 100 pcm range. These calculations were solved using the Python-NumPy eigenvalue routines in solver times of 0.06 and 0.016 seconds, respectively. The maximum relative scalar flux errors (for a test-case problem) for the models $ROM_{6,1}$, $ROM_{12,3}$, and $ROM_{18,3}$ were 5.8×10^{-4} , 2.6×10^{-5} , and

1.7×10^{-7} , respectively, demonstrating the rapid convergence of the model solutions.

Figure 3. Thermal scalar flux solutions for (testing-cases) moderation density 0.7 (top) and 0.3 (bottom) $\frac{g}{cm^3}$, comparing the FOM (left) ROM_{6,2} (middle) and ROM_{12,3} (right).

Figure 4. FOM eigenvalues and ROM k_{inf} errors (pcm) versus moderator density for various space-angle ROM resolutions; circles and squares indicate training and testing data.

4. CONCLUSION

This article has presented a new reduced-order model resolving the eigenvalue form of the neutron transport equations. The novelty lies in the combined generation and use of optimised space-angle

basis functions together with geometry-conforming structured grids, thereby enabling the ROMs to resolve complex domains - in this case, the fuel pins within an assembly. The method has been tested on a section of a BWR assembly where moderator densities were varied to represent changing conditions in a BWR core. The ROMs were successful in accurately resolving the eigenvalues and fluxes for new, unseen cases whilst reducing model sizes and solver times to values significantly below those of typical full-order models.

This article forms a foundation for efficient and accurate reduced-order models for reactor analysis, and opens the opportunity for further developments that extend on the application currently presented. Particular areas of interest would be extending to whole core transient analysis (through coupling to efficient thermal-hydraulic models) and potentially to burnup and core shuffling calculations. Such work will require further modifications to reduce the burden of working within large input parameter spaces, whilst capturing the large variations in flux distributions. This is left to future work.

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